

Sikhs- A Clan by Gurus

14 Comments / Blog / By Deepanshu Giri

This thought came to be on the night of Nirjala Ekadasi around 3 am in dreams, I noted down whatever I could remember but it make sense when I looked at the bigger picture, It was like connecting various dots to make a story.

Sikhism—the religion which follows the teachings of Guru, started after Guru Nanak dev ji originated in Punjab -The land of five rivers if we see from the point of Jyotish, the land of Punjab was the only place where this religion could have taken birth in full form and celebrated and practised in true form.

Punj-aab—the name comes from the five rivers of Punjab and Jupiter (Guru) is the planet which is exalted in Cancer- a watery sign- An emotional sign which can easily trust the words of Guru and be moulded by thoughts of Guru.

The emotion and innocence of Punjab which has a history of following the words of a guru to the extent that even the fight was in a ratio of 1/10 in Saragarhi or Chamkaur, warriors fought as it was the word of Guru.

Shaeed Bachittar Singh

The bread basket of India is a perfect trait of the Moon, feeding the whole country with love and pride, the concept of वंड छको—distribute and then consume is one of the important concepts of Sikhism, the entire religion is based on service for humanity to uplift others and this what Jyotish teaches us in terms of Guru, to help the community in whole.

The confidence in the word of the Guru has blessed this clan to be clean at heart, serve others and focus on God and never compromise on what you think is right as that is why fighting is an inseparable aspect of Sikhi, All the Gurus of this religion has made some great sacrifices such as Guru Arjan Singh refused to pay Jhajiya to Jahagir and accepted to die, while Guru Gobind Singh sacrificed his four sahibzaade.

**“हट कर चले वो हमसे जिसे सर अज़ीज़ हो ।
हम सरफ़िरो के साथ कोई सरफ़िरा चले । “**

The interesting thing is Guru & Air both go to head – An old saying “गुरु और हवा सिर पकड़ते है।” – As both of them have one work it to change your thoughts and thinking pattern. All the knowledge is in the book but what a mentor, teacher or Guru does is a change of thoughts and changing of thoughts happens when Guru has control over your breath- Which means till the time you are alive, every breath which goes through you must remind you of teachings of your Guru.

There cannot be a better example of this if we look at the religion of Sikhism, where gurus have led the charge to protect the community and their disciples followed it to the last breath.

If we take Jupiter in Cancer for Sikhism the 5th house becomes Scorpio, which is a house of Ketu and this planet can get the head chop but will not bow down as the 5th is also our pride and honour and for Cancer ascendants this becomes a matter of life and death but these natives never compromise. It was the chart of Cancer ascendants that took down Lanka barefoot, It is the clan of Cancer ascendants -Sikhism, which has fought great battles in the past for the country protecting honour and pride.

This clan has special rules for hair and tying a turban which shows their control over Saturn which brings resilience in bad times, and the ability to carry forward traditions, as your hair represents tradition when you shave your head it shows you have given and forgotten all the past experiences and relations which all other religion such as Buddhism will shave head so you can start your new journey, Sikhism says to carry forward the tradition of guru, never to cut your hair.

Baba Deep Singh Ji

As Saturn is a challenge for this community whenever Ketu Transits Scorpio and Saturn get powerful, then the area of Punjab suffers whether it's 1947,1965,1984 or 2021

There are countries which are associated with Saturn—Scorpio which is a comfortable house for Saturn belongs to England, While Capricorn is the US and Aquarius is Canada no wonder we found a considerable amount of Sikhs in these countries and have progressed in these regions.

If you are suffering from malefic effects of Guru in your chart which is happiness is missing from your life, You are not socially acceptable or getting due credit for your work, and Kids suffering in various areas of life- I would advise following the principles of Sikhism by having trust in your Guru, Serve in the temple or at your Guru's place without any expectation, Have compassion for serving others with a big heart.

Donate 10% of your income at your Guru's place and let them decide what to do with that money and slowly your way of life and thinking will change along with problems vanishing from your life.

Once Alexander was passing through a village and he saw a beautiful orchid of oranges after picking a few from the tree, he asked the farmer- how much for oranges? The vendor in local currency said 500Rs to which Alexander paid the money and asked his chief- are Oranges a rare commodity in this part of the world as this was a very expensive price?

To which the chief replied- **“No sir, Oranges are not rare but Kings are”**– He charged you according to your status -This one-line answer from the farmer made the king so happy that he gave extra money to the farmer.

Read the blog on why the distribution of food is only given to Kings- "[A Remedy only for the King. This is one remedy which can only be... | by Deepanshu Giri | Medium](#)"

This is the best advice I can give to you for you Jupiter- Be a real Sardar of your life by following the teaching of Guru and you will realise most of your life problems will go away.

The rest of the article with some more stories and specific remedies to Jupiter in various houses and signs- I have discussed in an upcoming magazine of Lunar Astro- If you haven't subscribed yet- [Click here](#)

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